

**Title: Experiences in the First Semester of Master's Degree Programme:
Reflective Report**

Institution: Universiti Brunei Darussalam

Programme: Master of Management

Module: BM5102 Organisational Behaviour

Registration Number: 20M1290

Date: 22 November 2020

Introduction

My journey as a Master student is similar to a rollercoaster from the very beginning, filled with expectations, thrills and anxiety, ups and downs. The past four months have been challenging and there are quite a few things that I would love to have done differently, and was expecting different outcomes - however, as it is now, I can only reflect on what has happened and learn from these experiences. In this report, I will briefly describe my experiences from the moment I decided to pursue higher education (Master's degree) before I continue with the rest of my reflection.

Before admission

Prior to writing this report, I reread a past assignment where Management students taking Organisational Behaviour module were asked to use theories and concepts in management to discuss our motivation to pursue a Master's degree. Before I was officially accepted into the Master's programme in Universiti Brunei Darussalam, my main motivation was only to "get a good job", which I will further elaborate in this report.

According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF) 2019 report, Brunei has an increasing rate of unemployment, especially among the youth. The report states that unemployment has increased to 28.9%, the highest among ASEAN and GCC countries. This is of importance because as unemployment becomes a major issue in Brunei, I am not hopeful for the prospect of my future job.

From a personal observation, getting employed immediately after obtaining a degree seems to be highly expected by everyone. The job must also preferably be prestigious and in the government sector, as there are better benefits and financial or work security compared to private sectors (Musa & Idris, 2020). Graduating in 2018 with a Bachelor's degree, the same expectations were also placed on me; I worked as a part-time staff in a food and beverage company - a physically demanding job, before pursuing a Master's degree. Alas, it was not an ideal job for me, and it was then I started questioning what kind of path I should take from there onward. The issue of unemployment remains a major concern, and I was in a dilemma: to continue with my current position in life or pursue higher education and improve my prospect?

Up until the deadline for the submission of the Master's programme application, I was still in a dilemma - whether I want to study again, whether I have the capacity to pursue higher education again. I noted a feeling of nervousness and excitement as the application deadline was approaching. Finally, after discussing with family members and friends, I submitted my application.

During the semester

First of all, I would like to elaborate on my motivation to pursue a Master's degree before continuing with the rest of my reflection. As I have stated, my sole motivation was to seek a good job, or a financially-stable job. Once I started attending university, I realized that my motivation is also affected by other factors. According to Maslow's hierarchy of needs (1943),

there are five stages of needs for any individual, which are arranged in a hierarchy. A person is motivated to fulfill a need until it is at least partially satisfied (as cited in Ramlall, 2004). Hence, my motivation is also affected by the “esteem” needs of the Maslow hierarchy, in which I seek respect and recognition for my effort, achievement and skills. Another motivational need is the “safety” need, where I seek security for my well-being. In this case, pursuing a stable job falls under this factor, as it is my priority to secure a stable life in the future. Moreover, these needs are also correlated to Vroom’s expectancy theory, which states that an individual’s effort is equivalent to the rewards from their action (Robbins, 1993, as cited in Ramlall, 2004). Hence, I exert my effort to pursue higher education with the expectations of obtaining rewards such as completing a Master’s degree and increasing my employability as well as specific skills and abilities. Throughout the semester, these are the factors that I always try to remember as a form of personal motivation.

When the semester started, I only came to realize how different the learning environment would be with social distancing and various restrictions implemented due to the pandemic COVID-19. For my modules, all lectures were conducted online. Although some tutorials were still conducted in a physical class, it was not as intensive as the online classes. Furthermore, the modules that I was taking in the first semester were all core modules and all four of them changed to coursework modules in response to COVID-19 restrictions. In other words, there were no examinations for these modules and hence the workload was much heavier compared to what I was used to. This new, changing environment itself was a challenging experience.

As the definition of distance learning is inconsistent, in this report it is loosely defined as an instructional environment between an instructor and a learner which can be conducted at various times as well as places using various forms of materials (Moore, Dickson-Deane & Galyen, 2011). The relationship between learning and various variables from the learner-related variables, such as individual cognitive style and motivation, to context variables which is the medium of learning has an impact on an individual’s learning process (Offir, Bezalel & Barth, 2007). As online classes are now the new norm, it is a situation that I need to get used to as distance learning does not seem to quite fit my learning style.

As both a visual and auditory learner, I find the idea of not seeing the lecturer directly in front of me slightly jarring as I am used to seeing them teaching in front of the classroom. Again, this is a new environment for me. Although many studies have criticized the learning style theory as it lacks supporting evidence, and a study conducted by Johnson et al. found that there was no significant differences between active and visual learners with reflective learners in terms of learning preferences, it is noted that active and visual learners preferred face-to-face study groups whereas reflective learners preferred online groups (as cited in Romanelli, Bird & Ryan, 2009).

In my case, I prefer learning topics which are more difficult in physical classes compared to online classes. One reason is I often lose attention when I cannot immediately understand a topic, so learning becomes less proficient (Galluch, Long, Bratton, Gee & Groeber, 2009). With the presence of distractions that are more likely to grab my attention when attending classes online, it makes it more difficult for me to grasp and comprehend the lecture content. Taneja, Fiore and Fischer (2015) conducted a study on students in a public college to determine factors that led to

cyber-slacking in the classroom. They found three main groups or drivers based on intention, attitude and lack of attention. Their findings suggest that escapism and lack of attention contribute to cyber-slacking. Possible causes are students not being interested in the class or finding the topic difficult so they used the Internet for non-class activities as a way to release discomfort. Similar reasons were found for the lack of attention as a driving factor.

On the other hand, online classes allow me to look up related terms or topics on the Internet to better understand the content from my lecturers without disrupting the flow of the online classes. Moreover, it helps expand my knowledge on a certain topic.

Needless to say, I am not claiming that online or distance learning is disadvantageous as there are aspects of it that are uniquely its strengths. Online learning with current COVID-19 restrictions means that I can stay at home to access lectures, lecture materials and in most cases, attend tutorials as well without having to go outside. I am able to limit physical contact with people, also known as “social distancing”, and so limit the risk of COVID-19 transmission. As long as I have an internet connection, I can access the module content from anywhere and at any time I want - unless the classes are set for a certain time in a week. This kind of flexibility is one major advantage of online learning.

The complexity of distance learning can be summarized briefly from a study on university students in Russia (Markova, Glazkova & Zaborova, 2017). Some of the findings indicate that 72% of the participants reported they were motivated to choose an online mode of study as it made it possible for them to work and study at the same time, while 58.6% agreed their choices were due to the possibility of studying from their place of residence; 26.1% stated learning flexibility as their reason. However, despite the students reporting positive evaluations of distance learning and staff competencies, 45.2% of the participants stated that distance learning does not promote interactive teacher-students’ communication while 30.5% agreed otherwise and 24.3% were unsure. The authors regard this as contributing to student isolation, which affected the students’ satisfaction with online learning, acting as a barrier to effective learning. They propose that the students, instructors and administration work together so as to improve the quality of distance learning.

Another issue I have with distance learning is forming or being in a group for group assignment with minimal physical interactions. As the classes were conducted online, there were almost no physical interactions with fellow coursemates. For groups work in the Organisational Behaviour module, groups were formed online based on the topic that the students were interested in. For the topic that I had chosen, I was to work with two other students. Although I had chosen a topic that seemed interesting and was excited about it, I was pretty nervous as well because of the lack of prior contact with any of the group members.

It is generally known that in a group of people, there is bound to be individual differences. This is remarkably so when none of the individuals are familiar with each other. This is obvious in my case. Furthermore, communication with group members was mainly conducted online through a messaging application. As such, navigating the group despite differences in working styles and communication styles is necessary.

One of the first things that I did was acquire a better understanding of our topic and in the process, convey my understanding towards my group members. This was my first step in trying to get a sense on how my group members learn and work with other people. It was also a way to “break the ice”, so to speak. I believe that the more familiar or closer individuals are, the more comfortable they become to offer opinions or suggestions in a group and hence, the more creative thinking is produced. Each individual gets to contribute and offer a different perspective from the rest.

I also believe in cooperation as well as communication among members in a group to achieve the desired results hence I often tried to instigate conversations in groups as much as possible. Fortunately, in this group we tried to help each other out as much as possible and clear up any confusions, which happened often as online communication is not as direct as face-to-face communication and miscommunication is typical. An interesting fact is that one group member stated that they are more comfortable working alone (physically) and so I never pushed them and adapted myself to the situation by dividing the task among ourselves so all of us had an idea of what we needed to do, as well as what the other members were doing.

To me, cooperative learning in a group of people is important for a better cohesion of ideas as individuals in a group are able to empathize with each other and understand others’ perceptions and hence work better together. From a study on language learners, Azizinezhad, Hashemi and Darvishi (2013) stated that cooperative learning encourages student participation and reduces learning anxiety. They also reported that as cooperative learning involves all members in a group, an individual is more likely to perform their task due to positive interdependence and accountability.

One major event happened during the semester which had a significant impact not only on me but also my group, as the faculty announced they are withholding primary data research as well as ethics approval. In other words, any primary research has to be changed to secondary research. This happened quite late in the semester which was devastating as we had spent weeks prior to the announcement coming up with questions for our research as well as reviewing extant literature after multiple times of fixing the research proposal. We also had created a list of questions to ask our interviewees and had started asking permission. The same situation is also applied for my individual assignment as permission for ethics approval and primary data collection for my individual research was not considered. Personally, this new rule is definitely the largest hurdle or challenge in this semester.

After a discussion with the lecturer during our class and further discussion with my group, we chose to carry out a systematic literature review instead. This meant that we had to change our topic and whole approach. I also decided to change my individual research to systematic review due to time constraint. As carrying out a systematic literature review is an entirely new experience, it was a daunting task to do. The last two months of the semester was a tough journey because of such unexpected changes. A lesson that I think can be taken from this is that “have a plan B” - ensure that whether it is for individual or group work, there must be another plan in case something does not go as planned. This is a lesson that I will remember.

A significant problem I experienced this semester was time-management. I was struggling to manage my time for group work and individual work as well as other assignments for other courses. Moreover, as I have mentioned, as most communication was online in all the groups that I was in, it was more difficult to set up a time for discussions especially when our schedules did not match or in case there were personal matters to attend to. Personally, it could get frustrating - but I also understood their situations very well.

As I think my learning challenges are related to issues of time-management, I would love to learn and improve my learning skills based on self-directed learning. Garrison (1997) proposes a comprehensive model for the concept of self-directed learning which consists of three dimensions: self-management, self-monitoring, and motivation. According to the author, each dimension is responsible for different factors although they are correlated. Self-management involves task control where the learner has the responsibility to manage their learning on their own. In this dimension, the learner needs to be conscious of their learning methods and goals as well as resources and support. The next one is self-monitoring, which includes cognitive responsibilities of the learner. In other words, the learner needs to construct meaningful ideas and concepts to develop new knowledge or add to existing ones in addition to engaging in reflective, critical thinking. Lastly, motivation is an important factor in learning as it is the factor which is involved in “initiation and maintenance of effort toward learning and the achievement of cognitive goals” (Garrison, 1997, p. 26), hence persistence in achieving learning goals is affected by the motivation of the learner.

End of the semester

When I look back at the motivation assignment, I would say that my motivational factors or needs have remained the same. However, I have not yet achieved my goals as I am lacking in many areas this semester, whether in terms of individual or group work. Aside from that, I am motivated to cultivate new skills which will be useful for me in the future, specifically to match these skills with what employers look for in jobseekers.

Continuous learning, in the form of self-directed learning, will be an advantage as it will help me manage my skills independently and with flexibility, and thus will ensure my skills are always up-to-date in an especially competitive job-seeking environment (Francom, 2010). As reported by Musa and Idris (2020), employers seem to emphasize self-awareness and leadership skills in employees. Hence, developing and polishing such skills now would be a benefit in the future.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I aim to learn to adapt to the new learning environment to avoid difficulties in understanding lessons as well as improving myself in terms of cultivating self-directed learning skills so I will not feel overwhelmed by distance learning in the next semester. I also aim to manage my time better and be more confident and assertive in communicating with group members so as to reduce the risk of miscommunication and social loafing and in turn, increase the efficiency of my group work. Overall, I would like to focus on improving my personal skills to achieve better performance in the future, whether in academics or to pursue employment in the future.

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